

Traditional Chinese Medicine for the Prevention and Management of Metabolic Diseases.

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Abstract: Background: Metabolic diseases, affecting the body's energy production and nutrient utilization, are increasingly prevalent globally. These pathologies are complex, involving genetic, epigenetic, socio-environmental, sociocultural, and psychosocial factors, and are often linked to insulin resistance, chronic inflammation, and hormonal imbalances. This review explores the multifaceted aetiology of metabolic diseases and delves into the therapeutic potential of Traditional Chinese Medicine approaches.

Methods: This review synthesizes current literature on the aetiology of metabolic diseases, including genetic and epigenetic factors, as well as the influence of lifestyle, environment, and psychosocial stress. It further examines the Traditional Chinese Medicine perspective on metabolic diseases, focusing on bioenergetic mechanisms, and explores the therapeutic applications of dietotherapy, phytotherapy, acupuncture, and moxibustion in managing these conditions. Relevant studies, including systematic reviews, meta-analyses, and clinical trials, were considered.

Results: From a traditional perspective, imbalances in Qi, particularly involving the Spleen-Pancreas and Liver, are central to the development of these conditions. The review further demonstrates the potential of Traditional Chinese Medicine therapies, including tailored diets, herbal formulas, acupuncture, and moxibustion, in addressing the underlying imbalances and managing metabolic diseases such as diabetes and obesity. Specific points and herbal formulas commonly used in TCM for these conditions are discussed.

Conclusions: This review suggests that Traditional Chinese Medicine offers promising complementary therapeutic strategies for the prevention and management of metabolic diseases. Further research, including rigorous clinical trials, is warranted to fully elucidate the efficacy and mechanisms of TCM interventions for metabolic diseases and to facilitate their integration into conventional healthcare systems.

Keywords: Obesity; Diabetes Mellitus; Metabolic Diseases; Traditional Chinese Medicine; Acupuncture; Herbal therapy; Diet; Moxibustion.

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1. Background

Metabolic diseases are pathologies that affect the body's metabolism, which is a set of biochemical processes responsible for energy production and the maintenance of cellular functions¹. These pathologies typically involve the way the body uses and/or stores nutrients such as carbohydrates, proteins, and lipids, and are frequently associated with hormonal dysfunctions and abnormalities in energy balance^{2,3}.

Biological mechanisms are crucial processes for maintaining health and preventing diseases, such as metabolic diseases. Affected mechanisms that may lead to metabolic diseases include, among others, insulin resistance, hormonal imbalances, chronic inflammation, oxidative stress, lipid dysregulation, gut microbiota dysfunction, and mitochondrial and endothelial dysfunction^{1,4}.

Insulin resistance involves the excessive flow of fatty acids released into adipose tissue and accumulated in other parts of the body, such as the liver and skeletal muscles, leading to adipose tissue dysfunction and impairing insulin receptors and secretion. In obesity, pro-inflammatory molecules (cytokines, adipokines, and chemotactic factors) are released from adipose tissue, which is called low-grade chronic inflammation^{5,6}. Excess nutrients and fat accumulation lead to increased production of reactive oxygen species, which damage proteins, lipids, and DNA, impairing insulin signalling and generating oxidative stress^{7,8}.

It is known that low-intensity chronic inflammation is present in various stages of chronic non-communicable diseases, such as metabolic diseases⁹⁻¹¹.

Studies have shown that the intestinal flora of an overweight person has less variety of bacteria as well as inflammatory markers in the blood¹²⁻¹⁴.

In addition, the effect of inflammatory bacterial substances hinders the work of the thyroid, which leads it to produce fewer hormones, making it slower to burn fat¹⁵. Low-grade chronic inflammation may not only be produced by bacteria but also by other factors, such as excess estrogen, vitamin D deficiency, poor diet or excessive gluten consumption¹⁶⁻¹⁹.

Alarming, the prevalence of metabolic diseases has been growing exponentially. A WHO report on obesity in Europe states that overweight and obesity rates have reached epidemic proportions across the region, where 59% of adults and almost 1 in 3 children are overweight or obese²⁰. On the other hand, the worldwide prevalence of diabetes, estimated in 2021, is about 10.5% among those aged 20 to 79, corresponding to 536.6 million people²¹.

1.1. Aetiology

According to Fan²², the aetiology of metabolic diseases is complex, with several factors potentially explaining part of the etiological "cascade."

At its base, the aetiology stems from genetic and epigenetic factors, and these, associated with behavioural risk factors, increase the likelihood of developing metabolic diseases.

Genetic Factors

At the level of genetic factors associated with so-called heredity, the predisposition to the prevalence of these pathologies comes from specific mutations called genetic polymorphisms, which are variations in genes.

According to Brown *et al.*²³, large-scale genome-wide association studies have helped to advance the identification of common genetic variations associated with insulin resistance and metabolic syndrome. More recently, exome sequencing has allowed the identification of rare variants associated with the pathogenesis of these conditions²⁴. According to the authors²³, many genetic variants involved in the pathogenesis of metabolic syndrome are associated with lipid metabolism.

Furthermore, Panera *et al.*²⁵ state that growing evidence suggests that genetic variation (typically single nucleotide polymorphisms) can also affect epigenetic profiles, independently or in combination with environmental factors.

Epigenetic Factors

Epigenetic factors influence how genes are expressed without altering the DNA. These are associated with our lifestyle, such as inadequate diet, sedentary behaviour, stress, poor sleep habits, and even gestational and early-life nutrition^{26,27}. Adequate nutrition begins in the first thousand days of life, from gestation to 2 years of age. It is essential to promote good nutrition, as this will impact the emergence or not of metabolic diseases²⁷.

After several studies suggested that insulin resistance is more likely in children who received formula milk than in children who received breast milk, a study by the World

Health Organization with a sample of more than 100,000 children aged 6 to 9 confirmed breastfeeding as a protective factor for childhood obesity ²⁸.

However, in general, an inadequate diet, rich in sugars, saturated fats, and processed foods, promotes inflammation, insulin resistance, and the accumulation of body fat ²⁹.

Sedentary behaviour is also closely associated with and present in our civilization, which leads to weight gain and increased insulin resistance ^{30,31}. Similarly, poor sleep habits increase inflammatory markers in the body, which contributes to insulin resistance ³²⁻³⁵.

Socio-environmental Factors

The social determinants of health, especially socio-environmental factors, play a crucial role in the prevalence of metabolic diseases such as obesity and diabetes. Thus, the complex interaction between the environment in which we live and our food and lifestyle choices significantly shapes our health status.

An excellent example is the proliferation of ultra-processed foods, fast food, and sugary drinks in low-income communities, which is an alarming phenomenon ³⁶. This abundant and accessible supply, often accompanied by lower prices, significantly contributes to the increased prevalence of obesity ³⁷. Several factors explain this relationship.

1. Ultra-processed foods are generally high in calories, saturated fats, added sugars, and sodium, and low in fibre, vitamins, and minerals ³⁸⁻⁴⁰. This unbalanced nutritional composition favours weight gain and the development of insulin resistance.
2. The food industry invests heavily in marketing aimed at children and adolescents, promoting the consumption of ultra-processed foods and encouraging unhealthy eating habits ^{41,42}. In addition, the ease and speed of preparing fast food makes it attractive to people with little time available to cook, such as workers with long hours and single parents ⁴³. As well, ultra-processed foods are often cheaper than fresh and natural foods, making them more accessible to families with limited incomes.
3. The physical environment in which we live directly influences our opportunities to engage in physical activity and adopt healthy lifestyle habits. The presence of green spaces, bike paths, and leisure areas promotes the practice of outdoor physical activities, which contributes to weight loss, improved cardiovascular health, and stress reduction ⁴⁴⁻⁴⁶.
4. Moreover, exposure to atmospheric and chemical pollutants can have a significant impact on metabolism and increase the risk of metabolic diseases. Epidemiological studies have shown associations between air pollution and increased prevalence of obesity, diabetes, and cardiovascular diseases ^{47,48}.

In this way, we can affirm that socio-environmental factors play a fundamental role in determining metabolic health. The availability and access to ultra-processed foods, the lack of green spaces, and exposure to pollution are just some examples of how the environment in which we live can influence our choices and increase the risk of chronic diseases. Public policies and health promotion programs must consider these factors when developing strategies to prevent and control metabolic diseases.

Sociocultural Factors

Culture plays a central role in defining the eating habits of people. Culinary traditions, celebrations, and social events are intrinsically linked to food ⁴⁹. In some cultures, for example, the consumption of ultra-processed foods and sugary drinks may be valued, while in others, the diet is based on fresh and natural foods. These cultural differences directly influence the composition of the diet and, consequently, the risk of metabolic diseases ^{50,51}.

In addition to culture, the level of education is associated with knowledge about nutrition and health ⁵². People with higher levels of education tend to have greater access to

information about healthy eating and to adopt more appropriate eating habits. However, even people with a high level of education can be influenced by other sociocultural factors that make it difficult to adopt healthy behaviours⁵³.

Psychosocial Factors

Chronic stress can trigger a series of physiological changes that contribute to the development of metabolic diseases⁵⁴. Increased levels of cortisol and other hormones can lead to insulin resistance, increased appetite, and abdominal fat deposition^{55,56}. In addition, stress can lead to the adoption of unhealthy behaviours, such as excessive consumption of ultra-processed foods and sedentary behaviour.

Closely related to stress, depression can play an important role, since depression and metabolic diseases have a bidirectional relationship^{57,58}. Depression can lead to changes in appetite, sleep, and physical activity, contributing to weight gain and the development of insulin resistance. On the other hand, metabolic diseases can increase the risk of developing depression. Integrated treatment of depression and metabolic diseases is essential to improve the quality of life of patients and reduce the risk of complications^{57,59}.

Also, social isolation is associated with several health problems, including metabolic diseases⁶⁰. People who live socially isolated tend to have less healthy lifestyle habits, such as excessive consumption of ultra-processed foods and insufficient physical activity. In addition, social isolation can lead to hormonal and inflammatory changes that increase the risk of chronic diseases⁶¹.

2. Metabolic Diseases and Traditional Chinese Medicine

2.1. Bioenergetic Mechanisms

The Eastern approach to metabolic diseases is characterized by a holistic perspective where prevention, energy balance, and harmony between body and mind are fundamental^{62,63}.

In Traditional Chinese Medicine, the focus is on the balance of vital energy, known as "Qi." According to this medicine, metabolic diseases derive from energy imbalances in the body that originate pathologies, influencing not only the energy system but also the organs^{64,65}.

This is based on the energy that flows through meridians, called energy channels in the body, to which poor circulation or insufficiency of *Qi* can lead to various diseases^{64,66}. The organs especially affected in metabolic diseases are the Spleen-Pancreas (*Pi*) and the Liver (*Gan*), both considered central to the processing and distribution of nutrients and energy. The Spleen-Pancreas is responsible for the transformation and transport of nutrients obtained from food, transforming them into *Qi* and Blood (*Xue*). When there is a deficiency in the Spleen-Pancreas, this can lead to poor digestion, chronic fatigue, and accumulation of 'dampness'. The Liver, on the other hand, regulates the smooth distribution of *Qi* and Blood in the body. Any stagnation or deficiency in Liver *Qi* can manifest as insulin resistance, hormonal imbalances, and chronic inflammation.

2.2. Diabetes Mellitus

According to the classic Huangdi Neijing⁶⁷, obesity is the result of overeating, and diabetes is referred to as the *Xiaoke* disease, which is a consequence of obesity. Complications of *Xiaoke* disease include stroke, carbuncle, and foot gangrene^{68,69}. In Chinese, *Xiao* means loss of body weight and *Ke* means thirst, which is similar to the symptoms of diabetes, that is, weight loss accompanied by increased fluid intake, eating, and urination. In Traditional Chinese Medicine theory, *Xiaoke* is considered the result of a deficiency of *Yin* with 'dry-heat'. The treatment of diabetes should focus on replenishing *Yin* (fluid) and evacuating 'fire' ('heat') from the body⁷⁰.

In addition, the production of 'heat' consumes *Yin*, harming the Lungs, Stomach, and Kidneys. This pathology can be induced by prolonged or sudden emotions that lead to

stagnation of Liver *Qi*, manifesting 'heat'. We can observe imbalances at the level of the three *jiaos*. The Upper *Jiao* is characterized by polydipsia (excessive fluid intake, dry mouth). The Middle *Jiao* is characterized by polyphagia (increased appetite, rapid digestion, and frequent hunger). The Lower *Jiao* is characterized by polyuria (frequent and urgent urination); we can also find a characteristic of sweet-smelling urine (glycosuria), the inability of the kidneys to reabsorb glucose.

2.3. Obesity

Obesity is another pathology of metabolic diseases and is characterized by an internal imbalance that leads the body to be unable to process and transform food effectively, leading to the accumulation of pathogenic substances such as 'dampness'/ 'phlegm'. This comes from an imbalance in the earth element, generating a spleen deficiency that leads to an accumulation of dampness/phlegm and stagnation of *Qi* and *Xue*^{71,72}. Emotions such as obsessive and constant thoughts and frustration or anger lead to the weakening of the Spleen and stagnation of Liver *Qi*, respectively.

Traditional Chinese medicine has long been used to treat diseases, playing an important role in the treatment of obesity^{72,73}.

3. Prevention and Management of Metabolic Diseases: Therapeutic Approaches in Traditional Chinese Medicine

3.1. Dietotherapy

Modern knowledge about nutrition and diseases is often based on the notion that vitamins proteins, carbohydrates, and fats are essential for a balanced diet, and that each of these has a specific function, being essential for maintaining the functions of the body⁷⁴.

Therapeutic dietetics in Chinese medicine has always been undervalued in the West, partly because the notions of the functioning of the human body follow particular principles, different from modern scientific notions, and on the other hand, due to the lack of access to these notions both in the literature and throughout history⁷⁴.

However, the history of Chinese dietotherapy is long-standing. Imperial herbalist doctors, aligned with Confucian schools, always gave importance to "achieving nutrition" by selecting foods in an almost philosophical way⁷⁵. It is important to mention that in these terms, "healing and nourishing come from the same source"⁷⁶.

For them, the choice was based on the appropriate quantity, neither in excess nor in scarcity, as well as having a diet based on a wide variety of foods. In section 22, chapter 81 of the Yellow Emperor's Classic of Internal Medicine⁷⁷⁻⁷⁹, some dietary recommendations are given, for example, the five cereals (rice, sesame seeds, soy, wheat, and millet) provide nutrition, the five fruits (date, plum, chestnut, apricot, and peach) produce complementarity (assist), the five animals (cow, dog, pig, chicken, and mutton) give advantage, the five vegetables (cucurbits, chives, sprouts, shallots, and onion) are for supplementing. According to Zhi-chien⁷⁵, these were probably the first dietary guidelines in the history of mankind in which both the satisfaction of nutritional and organic needs of the body was sought. These recommendations highlight the importance of a varied and complete diet.

Throughout history, various texts have been written on the therapeutic prescription/guidance of food as well as the preparation of meals⁷⁹. For example, in Su Wen⁷⁸, it is described that grains were boiled in soup as food for the five internal organs in ancient times. After boiling for some time, the grains fermented and turned into a puree, which can be used as a treatment for the five internal organs.

Also very important, in traditional Chinese dietotherapy, food should be in accordance with the various seasons of the year to comply with the laws of nature⁷⁹. For example, according to the recommendations present in *Principles of Correct Diet (Yinshan zheng-yao)*, written by the imperial physician Hu Sihui in the Yuan Dynasty, "in the heat of

spring, it is appropriate to eat wheat to refresh; in the heat of summer, it is appropriate to eat mung beans to cool down; in the dryness of autumn, it is appropriate to eat sesame seeds to nourish the dryness; in the cold of winter, it is appropriate to eat millet to dispel the cold".

Increasingly, the foundations of Chinese dietotherapy have been explored, bridging the gap to Western knowledge and allowing for greater understanding^{80,81}. The concrete action of Chinese dietotherapy in metabolic diseases comes mainly from its preventive capacity, not only for these pathologies but for all in general. After all, a correct and balanced diet is the basis for the balance of body and mind, as is also supported by the notion of the gut-brain axis^{62,82}.

The study by Yang *et al.*⁸³ refers to a specific form of *Yao-Shan* (or ancestral Chinese medicinal diet), used in Chinese cooking and drinks. In Table 1, the commonly used ingredients of *Yao-Shan* for *Xiao-Ke* (diabetes) can be observed.

Table 1. Yao-Shan ingredients commonly used for diabetes.

Lan	<i>Eupatorium fortunei</i>
Gouqizi	<i>Lycium barbarum</i>
Baiying	<i>Solanum lyratum</i>
Gegen	<i>Pueraria lobata</i>
Gualougen	<i>Trichosanthes kirilowii</i>
Zhimu	<i>Anemarrhena asphodeloides</i>
Fuping	<i>Lemna minor</i>
Wanggua	<i>Trichosanthes cucumeroides</i>

Indeed, the polysaccharides and flavonoids of *Gouqizi*⁸⁴⁻⁸⁶, polysaccharides and puerarin from *Gegen*⁸⁷⁻⁸⁹, mangiferin from *Zhimu*⁹⁰, and protein tyrosine kinase from *Gualougen*⁹¹, are antidiabetic bioactive molecules.

However, in this specific issue, it is difficult to separate Chinese dietotherapy from Chinese phytotherapy.

3.2. Phytotherapy

Chinese phytotherapy (or Chinese herbal medicine) has been developed over the centuries according to the plants available regionally⁹² and is, together with Ayurvedic herbal medicine, a world-renowned and currently still in use system^{93,94}.

Chinese phytotherapy follows the principles of Traditional Chinese Medicine, being simultaneously a preventive and interventional therapeutic technique.

The use of preventive phytotherapy fits into the approach of dietotherapy, as we saw earlier, and is based mainly on the use of plants in the preparation of food, and in simple infusions to maintain health.

However, phytotherapy is based on the use of specific combinations of plants and/or other mineral or animal components⁹⁵.

This way, it becomes easier to study the effects of phytotherapy on metabolic diseases.

For example, the study by Liu *et al.*⁹⁶ suggests that a formula composed of *Puerariae radix*, *Lycium barbarum*, *Crataegus pinnatifida*, and *Polygonati rhizome*, is capable of protecting against the development of diabetes and non-alcoholic fatty liver disease.

On the other hand, the *Xiao-Ke-Yin* formula was developed to treat metabolic diseases⁹⁷. This formula is composed of nine herbs, namely *Dioscorea Oppositifolia*, *Polygonatum Sibiricum*, *Rhizoma Polygonati Odorati*, *Folium Mori*, *Crataegus Pinnatifida*, *Rhizoma Phragmitis*, *Angelica Sinensis*, *Gardenia Jasminoides* and *Pueraria Lobata*. In fact, the study developed by Li *et al.*⁹⁷ provides evidence that this combination can produce therapeutic effects on glucolipid metabolism. The mechanisms of *Xiao-Ke-Yin* involve decreasing the gene expression of hepatic cholesterol biosynthesis. In addition, changes in the intestinal

microbiota were observed, reducing the levels of lithocholic acid and deoxycholic acid, thus promoting the synthesis of hepatic bile acids and inhibiting the FXR-FGF15 signalling pathway. It can also regulate the metabolism of amino acids (arginine biosynthesis; alanine, aspartate and glutamate metabolism; phenylalanine, tyrosine and tryptophan biosynthesis and tryptophan metabolism), which play an important role in the pathological process of metabolic diseases.

The study by Lian *et al.*⁹⁸ investigated the efficacy of the *Jinlida* formula in conjunction with metformin for the treatment of type 2 diabetes.

The composition of this formula consists of 17 herbs, including *Panax Ginseng*, *Polygonati*, *Atractylodis Lanceae*, *Sophorae Flavescens*, *Ophiopogon japonicus*, *Rehmanniae*, *Polygoni Multiflori*, *Dogwood*, *Poria*, *Perrin*, *Coptis Chinensis*, *Anemarrhena*, *Epimedium*, *Salvia*, *Puerariae*, *Semen Litchi*, and *Cortex Lycii Radicis*.

In this study, the results indicate that *Jinlida*, when combined with metformin, significantly reduces blood sugar levels (HbA1c, fasting and postprandial glucose) compared to metformin alone. It has also been shown to improve the function of beta cells, responsible for insulin production. These results suggest that *Jinlida* may be an effective adjunct treatment for patients with type 2 diabetes who do not achieve adequate glycemic control with metformin alone. This combination may represent a new therapeutic approach for diabetes, combining Western and traditional Chinese medicine.

In turn, Yu *et al.*⁹⁹ evaluated the efficacy of the *Jiangtang Tiaozhi* formula in the treatment of patients with type 2 diabetes with obesity and high blood lipid levels. The composition of *Jiangtang Tiaozhi* is formed by *Luhui* (*Aloe vera*), *Huanglian* (*Coptis Chinensis*), *Zhimu* (*Rhizoma Anemarrhenae*), *Hongqu* (red yeast rice), *Kugua* (*Momordica Charantia*), *Danshen* (*Salvia miltiorrhiza*), *Wuweizi* (*Schisandra Chinensis*), and *Ganjiang* (dried *Zingiber Officinale*). The formula proved to be as effective as metformin in reducing blood sugar levels. It was also able to reduce blood lipids slightly more than metformin and led to greater weight loss. It had benefits in insulin resistance and increased insulin production compared to metformin.

Thus, the study showed that *Jiangtang Tiaozhi* appears to be a safe and effective alternative for the treatment of patients with type 2 diabetes with obesity and high blood lipid levels, especially those who do not tolerate metformin. It may offer additional benefits in weight reduction and improved insulin sensitivity.

In agreement with these studies, Zhang *et al.*¹⁰⁰ state that traditional Chinese phytotherapy significantly improves glucose and lipid metabolism by modulating the intestinal microbiota. It further states that it can affect the abundance of mucin-degrading bacteria, bacteria with anti-inflammatory properties, bacteria-producing lipopolysaccharides and short-chain fatty acids, and bacteria with bile salt hydrolase activity. Finally, states that Chinese phytotherapy can protect intestinal barrier function, modulate metabolic endotoxemia and inflammatory responses, regulate the effects of short-chain fatty acids, modulate the gut-brain axis, regulate bile acids and tryptophan metabolism, and therefore has promising potential for the treatment of metabolic diseases.

3.3. Acupuncture

Just as dietotherapy and phytotherapy overlap in some ways, the same happens with acupuncture and phytotherapy. This refers to phytoacupuncture.

While acupuncture is defined as the needling of specific points or areas of the body, usually located along the channels or conduits where vital energy (*Qi*) is believed to circulate¹⁰¹⁻¹⁰³, phytoacupuncture involves application through (1) dipping the tips of the needles in plant decoctions before insertion, or (2) injecting a certain volume of the decoction to be used, improving the effectiveness of both techniques¹⁰⁴.

In this topic, a systematic review conducted by Santos *et al.*¹⁰⁵ sought to analyze the effects of acupuncture and phytoacupuncture in the treatment of obesity. The results showed that acupuncture can significantly reduce body mass index compared to controls,

further suggesting that it may work through the regulation of hormones related to metabolism and appetite. In the case of phytoacupuncture, although the results are more varied, some studies have shown significant reductions in waist circumference and improvements in metabolic activity. Thus, the authors conclude that acupuncture and phytoacupuncture can be valuable tools for the management of excess weight, especially when used in conjunction with other healthy lifestyle practices.

Table 2 presents the acupuncture points and most used formulas in the studies analyzed by Santos *et al.* ¹⁰⁵.

Table 2. The most used acupuncture points and formulas in the studies.

Main Acupuncture points	Used formulas
Stomach: ST20, ST23, ST24, ST25, ST26, ST36, ST40.	<i>Ephedra sinica</i> + <i>Aconitum carmichaeli</i> .
Spleen-Pancreas: SP6, SP9	<i>Bigiheo</i> : <i>Panax Ginseng</i> , <i>Astragalus Membranaceus</i> , <i>Discorea Batatas</i> , <i>Atractylodes Japonica</i> , <i>Poria Cocos</i> , <i>Citrus Unshiu</i> , <i>Zizyphus Jujube e Glycyrrhiza Uralensis</i> .
Conception vessel (Renmai): CV4, CV6, CV9, CV10, CV12.	<i>Sobeium</i> : <i>Platycodon grandiflorum</i> , <i>Ephedra Sinica</i> , <i>Morus Alba</i> , <i>Liriope Platyphylla</i> , <i>Scutelaria Baicalensis e Prunus Armeniaca</i> .
Other channels used: Lung, Small Intestine, Heart, Bladder, Sanjiao, Gallbladder, Liver, and Governing Vessel (Dumai).	<i>Bangkihwangkitang</i> : <i>Stephania Tetandra</i> , <i>Astragalus Membranaceus</i> , <i>Atractylodes Koreana</i> , <i>Glycyrrhiza Uralensis e Zingiber Officinale</i> .

Another systematic review, this time with meta-analysis, by Li *et al.* ¹⁰⁶ investigated the effectiveness of acupuncture for metabolic diseases.

In general, acupuncture monotherapy proved to be equally effective as conventional medications in controlling triglyceride and high-density lipoprotein (HDL) levels. When combined with lifestyle changes, acupuncture showed significantly better results in reducing waist circumference and body mass index.

Thus, the authors suggest that acupuncture may be effective in treating metabolic diseases, serving as an alternative or complement to conventional treatment. Table 3 shows the main acupuncture points used in the studies analyzed by the authors.

Table 3. Main channels and points according to the studies.

Canais	Pontos
Conception vessel (Renmai)	CV12, CV6, CV10, CV4.
Stomach	ST36, ST25, ST40.
Spleen-pancreas	SP6, SP15, SP9.
Bladder	BL20, BL21, BL18.
Large Intestine	LI4

3.4. Moxibustion

Regarding moxibustion, this is the application of heat to specific acupuncture points using medicinal herbs, particularly mugwort ¹⁰⁷. It can be applied suspended over the chosen point and/or using the acupuncture needle.

Studies suggest that the mechanism of action of this technique is due to its stimulating thermal effect, radiation effect, or even the biological activities of the medicinal herbs

used and their smoke^{108,109}. In any case, moxibustion appears to improve blood circulation¹¹⁰ and activate the immune system¹¹¹.

In an experimental study¹¹², the effect of suspended moxibustion on the biochemical markers of subjects with high cholesterol was analyzed.

Using moxibustion at points CV8 and ST36, it was observed that after 12 weeks of treatment, fasting glucose, total cholesterol, low-density lipoprotein (LDL), and triglyceride levels decreased significantly. Only HDL levels did not change. Based on these results, the authors suggest that suspended moxibustion on these two points may improve lipid metabolism and regulate glucose metabolism.

A meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials¹¹³ sought to evaluate the effectiveness of acupuncture with moxibustion in the treatment of obesity in adults. The results indicated that body mass index, weight, waist circumference, and triglyceride levels were significantly benefited by the intervention compared to controls. However, they found that high- and low-density lipoprotein (HDL and LDL) and cholesterol levels were not improved. According to these results, it is possible to suggest that acupuncture with moxibustion may be useful in the treatment of obesity in adults.

The authors also analyzed the frequency of use of acupuncture points by the studies included in the review, indicating that these (Table 4) may form the basis of obesity treatment.

Tabela 4. Basic points for the treatment of obesity in adults.

Channels	Points
Stomach	ST25, ST36, ST40.
Conception Vessel (<i>Ren Mai</i>)	CV12, CV6.

Thus, it can be stated that there is some evidence that supports the use of moxibustion to aid in the treatment of metabolic diseases.

4. Final considerations and conclusions

Despite the exploration made on the subject in question, some considerations should be made.

First, it is essential to contextualize the adherence of patients to these approaches, namely Traditional Chinese Medicine. It is essential to develop awareness actions of the population to the problem of metabolic diseases so that they can be more receptive to treatments and lifestyle changes. Also, informing about the possible effectiveness of Traditional Chinese Medicine techniques in this problem should be the next step to ensure more options for patients, mainly ensuring their complementary use to conventional treatments.

In this sense, it is important to mention that a multidisciplinary approach is viable and beneficial. Thus, it becomes essential to integrate different health professionals and areas of knowledge to offer more complete and personalized care. This way, the very changes in behaviour and life habits can be better sustained and lasting.

In addition, the development of these multidisciplinary actions in a hospital context and the national health system allows for greater accessibility through greater supply and decreased costs. The preventive treatment of metabolic diseases will, in the future, allow for a lower expense of the state itself in the treatment of consequent chronic complications.

Finally, following the principles of Traditional Chinese Medicine, it is important and beneficial to adapt and individualize treatments according to each patient. Not only will the integration of Traditional Chinese Medicine in public health care bring this benefit, but also integration in a multidisciplinary team may help to achieve this crucial goal.

Thus, we can conclude that Traditional Chinese Medicine has the potential to benefit the prevention and treatment of metabolic diseases, and it is necessary to continue investigating the effects of its techniques.

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